

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES AND ETHNOMEDICINAL REVIEW OF *EUPHORBIA*: NATURE'S DIVERSE HEALING RESERVOIR

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ABSTRACT

In this review, we looked at medicinal plants that are used to treat various illnesses. These are a few of the naturally occurring herbal plants that have a wide range of chemical components that are used to cure different diseases. Because of their high activity and lack of side effects, herbal plants play a significant role in treatment. The taxonomy distribution, colloquial names, phytoconstituents, morphology, pharmacological activity, medicinal applications, conclusion, and references of the plants were all examined in this review. *Euphorbiaceus* is commonly known as Barki-thohar. This plant is native to America but has become acclimatised and grows freely in all parts of India. This is a common medicinal plant of India the plant parts used milky juice and stem bark. Milky juice in small doses is a purgative but in large doses it is acrid, counter-irritant and emetic. *E. tirucallil* latex seems to reduce the specific cellular immunity associated with the virus

Epstein-Barr injection by activating the virus lytic cycle. The bark / latex of *E. tirucalli* presents pharmacological activities as an antibacterial, molluscicide, antiherpetic and anti-mutagenic. It also shows co-carcinogenic and anticarcinogenic activities. In the northeast region in Brazil, the latex of *E. tirucalli* is used as a folk medicine against syphilis. As an antimicrobial; a laxative agent to control intestinal parasites to treat asthma, cough, earache, rheumatism, verrucae, cancer, epithelioma, sarcoma and skin tumors. *E. tirucalli* contains a

large quantity of terpenes and sterols among its constituent and the following substances which have been isolated; alcohol eufol, alfaeuforbol and taraxa sterol e tirucallol. This review highlights the existing information particularly on the phytochemistry and various pharmacological properties of *Euphorbia tirucalli* which may provide incentive for proper evaluation of the plant as a medicinal agent.

KEYWORDS: *Anantibacterial, laxative-agent, pharmacological activity, phytoconstituent co-carcinogenic.*

INTRODUCTION

In spite of great advances of modern scientific medicine, traditional medicine is still the primary form of treating diseases of the majority of people in developing countries including India; even among those to whom western medicine is available, the number of people using one form or another of complementary or alternative medicine is rapidly increasing worldwide. Over the centuries humans have relied on plants for basic needs such as food, clothing, and shelter, all produced or manufactured from plant matrices (leaves, woods, fibers) and storage parts (fruits, tubers). Many plant-derived compounds have been used as drugs, either in their original or semi-synthetic form. The World Health Organisation estimates that about 80% of the population living in the developing countries rely almost exclusively on traditional medicine for their primary healthcare needs. India is the largest producer of medicinal herbs and is appropriately called the botanical garden of the world.

In recent years, the use of herbal medicines worldwide has provided an excellent opportunity to India to look for therapeutic lead compounds from an ancient system of therapy, i.e. Ayurveda, which can be utilized for development of new drug. *Euphorbia L. Euphorbioideae* is considered the second largest genus in the angiosperms, including ca. 2000 species. The Euphorbiaceae family includes trees, succulents and herbaceous plants. Different species of

Euphorbia grow all over the world, either wild, or as cultivated specimens in the house or garden.

Euphorbiaceae is among the large flowering plant families consisting of a wide variety of vegetative forms some of which are plants of great importance. Its classification and chemistry have of late been subjects of interest possibly because of the wide variety of chemical composition of its members, many of which are poisonous but useful. The worldwide distribution of the family exposes its members, to all sorts of habitats to which they must adapt, therefore inducing a large variety of chemicals (secondary substances) that are employed for survival/defence. *Euphorbiaceae* is generally distinguished by the milky sap. *Euphorbiaceae* comprises nearly 322 genera and 8910 species many of which have their own economic value and hence contribute to the floristic wealth of tropical and subtropical countries of the world.

Botanical Description

E. tirucallis is a succulent, cactus-like (FAO) spineless, unarmed, much-branched, monoecious or more often dioecious, easy to recognize, perennial shrub or tree up to 10–15 m tall.

Trunk or stem

The rubber-hedge euphorbia reach usually 2-5 m but may grow up to 15 m on occasion with a 2-4 m spread. The main trunk and branches are woody and brownish and may thicken up to a diameter of 25 cm. It grows with single or multiple trunks. The bark of very old specimens is grey and rough with longitudinal dents and ridges that break up into very small fragments. There are sometimes conspicuous, small protuberances, such as a bulge, knob, or swelling, on the bark, and occasionally black, rough, crosswise bands.

Branches

E. tirucallis a plant very branched with branches often arranged in pseudo whorls forming brush-like masses that are the best known feature of this species.

Leaves

Leaves are rarely seen as they fall very early or quickly (early deciduous), tiny, few, simple, fleshy, small or minute, slender and alternate. The leaf blade is linear-lanceolate to oblanceolate, 1–2.5 cm long, 3–4 mm broad and 2 mm thick, acute at tip, tapered to the

sessile base, arranged spirally, present only at the tips of young branchlets. The extreme tips of young leafy branchlets are sparsely tomentose, with curled brown hairs, and soon glabrescent. Stipules are minute, glandular and dark brown. The function of the leaves is taken over by the green branches.

Flowers

Plants are monoicous or dioicous, the chromosome number is 20 and the diploid number is 2n. The flowers are small or very small, yellow, green or pink arranged in groups on the terminal branches, discreet, and grouped at the top of the short branches, in heads, stalkless at the end of twigs, and carried in clusters at the apex of the short branches or in the angles of branches.

Fruits

Fruits are tripartite capsule and a capsule measures about 8-12 mm in diameter, is subglobose (nearly globose), almost glabrous or glabrescent, longitudinally very slightly lobed, short-stalked (8 mm), bent at an angle, pale green, with a pink tinge and conspicuously pubescent (soft hairs). Capsules dehisce while still on the tree, and exerted on a tomentose pedicel to 1 cm long.

Seeds

The seeds are ovoid (oval), about 3-4 mm x 2.8-3 mm, glabrous, smooth, buff speckled with brown and with a dark brown ventral line (with a white line), around the small white caruncle 1 mm across.

Latex

The latex is a caustic milky white sap when damaged, like many other *Euphorbia* species.

Root system

The plant produces lateral roots that do not grow very deep.

Euphorbia tirucalli Plant.

Plant Extract

Extraction, as the term is used pharmaceutically, involves the separation of medicinally active portions of plant or animal tissues from the inactive or inert components by using selective solvents in standard extraction procedures. The purposes of standardized extraction procedures for crude drugs are to attain the therapeutically desired portion and to eliminate the inert material by treatment with a selective solvent known as menstrum. The extract thus obtained may be ready for use as a medicinal agent in the form of tinctures and fluid extracts, it may be further processed to be incorporated in any dosage form such as tablets or capsules, or it may be fractionated to isolate individual chemical entities such as ajmalicine, hyosine and vincristine, which are modern drugs.

Thus, standardization of extraction procedures contributes significantly to the final quality of the herbal drug. General Methods of Extraction of Medicinal Plants- Maceration, Infusion, Digestion, Decoction, Percolation, Hot Continuous Extraction (Soxhlet), Aqueous Alcoholic Extraction by Fermentation, Counter-current Extraction, Ultrasound Extraction (Sonication), Supercritical Fluid Extraction and Phytonics Process *E. tirucalli* can be extracted in methanol, chloroform, pet ether, acetone for various activities.

Ethnomedicinal Uses

Just like the complexity in classification, ethnomedicine of Euphorbiaceae is very diverse. This diversity is due to the presence of a wide range of unusual secondary metabolites that makes most of the members poisonous. In addition, some members are said to cause or influence susceptibility to certain body ailments. For example *E. leuconera*, *tirucalli*, *J. curcas* and others are known to be co-carcinogenic and can influence/promote excessive cell division resulting in tumour growth. Also latex of *E. tirucalli* and *E. Royleana* is known to cause conjunctivitis on contact with eyes. In the northeast region of Brazil, the latex of *E. tirucalli* is used; as an antimicrobial agent; a laxative agent; to control intestinal parasites; to treat asthma, cough, earache, rheumatism, verrucae, cancer, chancre, epithelioma, sarcoma, skin tumors and as a folk remedy against syphilis.

Uses Traditional Medicine

Possibly due to a great variety of chemical substances found in *E. tirucalli* tissues, medical folklore literature of different parts of the world (especially tropical and subtropical areas where it is endemic) is tainted with its curative ability. In East Africa, latex is used against sexual impotence, warts, epilepsy, toothache, hemorrhoids, snake bites, extraction of ecto-

parasites and cough among others. In Peninsular Malaysia, a poultice of the roots or stems is applied to nose ulceration, haemorrhoids and swellings. Root scrapings mixed with coconut oil are taken for stomach-ache. In India, it is an unavoidable plant in most traditional homesteads and used as a remedy for ailments such as : spleen enlargement, asthma, dropsy, leprosy, biliousness, leucorrhoea, dyspepsia, jaundice, colic, tumors and bladder stones.

The latex of vesicant and rubifacient is emetic in large doses, it is purgative in small doses and applied against toothaches, earaches, rheumatism, warts, cough, neuralgia and scorpion bites. The same author points out that its branch and root decoctions are administered for colic and gastralgia while ashes are applied as caustic to open abscesses. In Brazil, *E.tirucalli*s used against cancer, cancroids, epitheliomas, sarcomas, tumors and warts, although they argue that this has no scientific basis since the same tree is known to be co-carcinogenic.

In Malabar (India) and the Moluccas, latex is used as an emetic and anti-syphilitic while in Indonesia, the root infusion is used for aching bones while a poultice of roots or leaves is used to treat nose ulcers, hemorrhoids and extraction of thorns. Wood decoctions are applied against leprosy and hands and feet paralysis following childbirth. The same author states that in Java, the plant latex is used to cure skin ailments and bone fractures.

Antimicrobial Activity

Acetone extracts of the stem of *E. tirucalli* were inhibitory to all the test microorganisms. *E. coli* was found to be highly sensitive to the acetone extracts of *E. tirucalli*. The MIC was 500 µg for *C. albicans* and 750 µg for *A. niger* and *A. fumigatus*. The chloroform extracts of the stem of *E. tirucalli* are active against *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris*, *S.aureus*, *A. niger* and *C. albicans* and the minimum inhibitory concentration was 250 µg for *P. vulgaris*, 500 µg for *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, while it was 750 µg against *B. subtilis* and *C. albicans*, 1000 µg for *A. niger*. The methanol extracts of the stem of *E. tirucalli* showed activity against *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *E. faecalis*, *S. aureus* and *C. albicans* and its minimum inhibitory concentration was found to be 500 µg for *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, while it was 750 µg for *B. subtilis*, *E. faecalis* and 1000 µg for *C. albicans*. The petroleum ether and hexane extracts did not show activity against the test organisms.

Antiherpetic Activity

To evaluate the capacity of the extracts to inhibit the lytic activity of herpes simplex virus type 2 (HSV-2) and the reduction of viability of infected or uninfected cell cultures, the end-point titration technique (EPTT) and the MTT [3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide] colorimetric assay were used, respectively. The therapeutic index of the positive extracts for the antiviral activity was determined by calculating the ratio CC (50% cytotoxic concentration) over IC₅₀ (50% inhibitory concentration of the viral effect). Five of the 47 extracts (11%) representing 3 out of 10 *Euphorbia* species (30%) exhibited antiherpetic action; the highest activity was found in the leaf/stem water-methanol extracts from *E. cotinifolia* and *E. tirucalli*.

Antioxidant Activity

A systemic and scientific investigation of aqueous extract of *E. tirucalli* for its antioxidant, Antioxidant property was assessed by using reducing property, superoxide anion scavenging and hydroxyl radical scavenging property. The aqueous extract has demonstrated dose-dependent in vitro antioxidant property (at 20 µg, 40 µg, 60 µg, 80 µg, 100 µg) in all the models of the study.

CONCLUSIONS

As per the literatures, most of the pharmacological activities were performed on latex of *E. tirucalli* by in-vitro and in-vivo experimental techniques. However, there is a need to explore molecular mechanisms for all the reported activities of *E. tirucalli*. There is lacking of isolation, structural elucidation and confirmation many more phytoconstituents by sophisticated instrumental analysis techniques from the plant. Exploration of toxicity of reported phytoconstituents is yet to be performed. *E. tirucalli* is not mentioned in Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India, it should be incorporated.

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